

Spinel Glass Fibers for Application in Solid-State Batteries

Nikola Klusoňová^{a*}, Eliška Sedláčková^a, Richard Bursa^a, Václav Procházka^a, Pavla Dvořáková^a,
Kristýna Jílková^a, Ondřej Jankovský^b, Jan Macháček^a, Martin Havlík Míka^a

^a*Department of Glass and Ceramics, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6 – Dejvice, Czech Republic*

^b*Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6 – Dejvice, Czech Republic*

* Corresponding author

E-mail address: Nikola.Klusonova@vscht.cz

Abstract

All-solid-state batteries are currently considered one of the most reliable battery systems, as they are nonflammable and do not form dendrites during the charging cycle, unlike liquid electrolyte batteries. Additionally, they are expected to offer higher energy density compared to current batteries. This work focuses on the preparation of a material that could serve as a cathode in all-solid-state batteries. The cathode material was obtained from end-of-life batteries, which enabled its reuse, and was used as a filler in glassy nano/micro-fibers prepared by electrospinning. Using the material in the form of nano/micro-fibers is expected to shorten the diffusion lengths of lithium ions, increase capacity, and improve the flexibility and stability of the material during cycling.

Keywords

Nanoparticles, composite materials, fiber technology, nanocomposites

1. Introduction

The lithium ion battery (LIB) is characterized by high energy and power density, long life, and environmental friendliness; therefore, it is widely used in consumer electronics, hybrid power,

and electric vehicles (EVs) [1-3]. However, conventional liquid electrolytes pose significant safety risks, including leakage, ignition, and even explosion when overheated. Solid-state electrolytes are regarded as the optimal solution to these safety issues due to their exceptional thermal and electrochemical stability, which also allows higher operating temperatures. In addition to increased safety, this type of battery should also be more cost-effective and have a higher energy density and a longer cycle life [4-6]. The chemical composition of solid-state battery cells does not differ from that of liquid electrolyte cells, with carbon, titanates, Li alloys and lithium metals used for the anode and Li-based oxides, phosphates and vanadium dioxide for the cathode [5].

The provision of a sustainable and practical solution to complex demands, such as the application of nanotechnology in batteries, has been the subject of intensive research for several years. This area has been studied repeatedly and has been considered a highly probable solution. Nanotechnology enables a wide range of material and chemical combinations, and many studies show that nanofibrous layers formed by electrospinning are a suitable structure for advanced electrical applications, for example, as electrodes in solid-state batteries [7, 8].

In this study, active material from commercially available NMC622 cathodes was used and mixed with a solution of high molecular weight polymer polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) and tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) [9]. Using electrospinning, layers of nano/microfibers were prepared, which could potentially be utilized as cathodes for all-solid-state batteries. The prepared layers were analyzed primarily in terms of chemical composition and thermal stability.

2. Material and methods

The NMC active material was obtained from an end-of-life LIB module commonly used in battery electric vehicles (BEVs). The module was short-circuited and then manually disassembled into its constituent parts, with the individual cells being separated. The LIB pouch cell was disassembled into individual layers of cathodes, anodes, and separators [10]. The cathode

material, along with the aluminum foil, was manually cut into 25×25 mm squares. These pieces were placed in a porcelain crucible and subjected to heat treatment in an electric furnace at $400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 60 min, with a temperature rise of $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ in an air atmosphere. After sintering and spontaneous cooling, the active material was separated from the aluminum foil in distilled water using a SONOPULS HD 2200.2 ultrasonic homogenizer, equipped with an GM 2200.2 ultrasonic generator and a UW 2200 ultrasonic converter (all by BANDELIN, Germany). The mixture of distilled water and particles was then sieved to remove aluminum foil and the water was evaporated at $95\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to achieve a constant weight. Finally, the particles were passed through a 40-micron mesh sieve for further refinement.

For the basic sol-gel, the following chemicals were used: PVP ($M_w \sim 1\,300\,000$, Sigma-Aldrich), colloidal TEOS (Sigma-Aldrich), methanol-denatured ethanol (EtOH), distilled water and hydrochloric acid (HCl, Lach-Ner, s.r.o.). The NMC powder was mixed with a PVP solution (PVP dissolved in EtOH) and a TEOS solution (TEOS + HCl + EtOH + H₂O) in a weight ratio of 2:2.5:1. After homogenization, fibers were prepared using an EF050 Needle Starter Kit electrospinning device (SKE Research Equipment) at a rate of 1 mL/h (sample NMC1un). The fibers were then calcinated at $650\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for one hour with a heating rate of $1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ (sample NMC1sint). The applied voltage was 20 kV, the distance from the collector was 15 cm, and the viscosity of the suspensions was 0.141 Pa·s. The prepared fibers were analyzed using SEM, XRF, XRD, and STA-MS. Confocal microscope images were also utilized for image analysis.

3. Results and discussion

The powdered material was analyzed using a LEXT OLS 5000 SAF (Olympus) laser confocal microscope, which enabled the measurement of the particle size distribution (see Fig.1). The analysis revealed that the median particle size is $d_{50}=9.24\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. All the particles analyzed have a size smaller than $12.59\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The analysis was performed repeatedly, and the results presented described at least 5000 particles.

Fig. 1. Particle size distribution graph.

Fig. 2 presents images from a scanning electron microscope (SEM) acquired in secondary electrons mode using the SEM VEGA 3 LMU (TESCAN). The working distance was 5.87 mm and the applied voltage was 20 kV. Images 2a,b depict a fiber layer prepared from 2 mL of the initial solution and electrospun at a rate of 1 mL/h. The images show that the NMC particles are embedded within the fibers. Images 2c,d show the same fiber layer after calcination at 650 °C. Calcination caused the fibers to shrink by approximately 30 %. The calcinated fibers are much thinner and the particles of the NMC material are more visible within them.

Fig. 2. SEM pictures taken from samples (a) NMC1un at magnification 2000; (b) NMC1sint at magnification 10000; (c) NMC1sint at magnification 2000; (d) NMC1sint at magnification 10000.

The XRF analysis (WD-XRF Axios, PANalytical) of the chemical composition (see Table 1) identified silicon dioxide, nickel oxide, manganese oxide, and cobalt oxide as the main elements. Other minor elements were aluminum oxide, phosphorus pentoxide, and tungsten oxide. Aluminum oxide is used as a current collector; therefore, a small amount was released during the separation of the NMC material from the aluminum foil. Phosphorus oxide likely originates from residual electrolyte, and tungsten oxide is used in the cathode, for example, to improve electron conductivity.

Table 1

Chemical composition in wt.% analyzed by XRF in fibers before sintering (NMC1un) and after sintering (NMC1sint).

Analyzed composition (wt.%)	Sample	
	NMC1un	NMC1sint
Al ₂ O ₃	0.89 ± 0.03	1.24 ± 0.03
SiO ₂	58.66 ± 0.10	58.62 ± 0.10
P ₂ O ₅	0.65 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.03
MnO	6.27 ± 0.07	6.54 ± 0.07
Co ₃ O ₄	5.64 ± 0.07	5.90 ± 0.07
NiO	27.30 ± 0.10	26.33 ± 0.10
WO ₃	0.59 ± 0.02	0.56 ± 0.02

Fig. 3a,b illustrate the simultaneous thermal analysis combined with mass spectroscopy of the NMC1un fibers prior to sintering, showing three distinct stages of weight loss. The analysis was

carried out using a Setsys Evolution apparatus (Setaram) with a flow rate of 50 mL/min and a heating rate of 10 °C/min in a dynamic air atmosphere. The initial weight loss, occurring between 50 °C and 300 °C, is attributed to the evaporation of volatile compounds such as moisture, solvents, and monomers. The second stage, between 300 °C and 360 °C, with an exothermic peak at 340 °C, probably corresponds to the decomposition of organic intermediates (TEOS), including the breakdown of PVP side chains. The third stage, from 360 °C to 488 °C, with an exothermic peak at 465 °C, is associated with the decomposition of the PVP main chains [11]. After sintering at 650 °C, an additional minor weight loss is observed, which is probably due to the thermooxidation and subsequent mass loss of the initial NMC material.

X-ray diffraction (PANalytical X'Pert Pro, PANalytical) (see Fig. 3c) of the NMC1un sample confirmed the presence of the crystalline phase NMC622, corresponding to the initial powder material. An amorphous peak is also observed in the diffractogram caused by the PVP polymer used in fiber preparation. Additionally, a minor crystalline phase of LiF, originating from the original electrolyte used in this type of battery, was identified. After subsequent calcination (sample NMC1sint, see Fig. 3d), changes in composition were observed, with the main crystalline phase identified as $\text{Li}_{0.25}\text{Mn}_{0.15}\text{Ni}_{0.6}$ (55 wt.%). Other identified phases include Li_2SiO_3 (35 wt.%) and LiC_6 (10 wt.%), and all phases present are indicated in the diffractogram. No amorphous phase is observed in the diffractogram as the polymer has been removed by sintering.

a)

b)

Fig. 3. (a) Thermal analysis of the unsintered sample: heat flow and weight loss and (b) relative intensity of released gases; (c) XRD analysis of NMC1un and (d) NMC1sint.

4. Conclusions

In this study, an ultrasonic probe was employed to successfully separate the active material from the aluminum current collector of end-of-life batteries. The recovered material was then utilized as a filler in fiberglass. The resulting fibers, produced by electrospinning, exhibited nano/micro dimensions. The initial chemical composition of the material corresponded to NMC622. However, structural changes were observed after calcination of the fibers. Remarkably, the fibers demonstrated thermal stability up to at least 1000 °C, indicating their potential for high-temperature applications.

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